

Nanophase Sn composite anodes for Li-ion batteries^ψ

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Two different nanophase Sn composites; one containing an inactive metal (Cu) matrix and the other an inactive ceramic (Li_2O) matrix were investigated as replacement anodes for graphite in Li-ion batteries. The nanophase Sn-Cu composite was prepared by a chemical route whereas the nanophase Sn- Li_2O composite was prepared by an *in situ* ball milling method. Electrochemical testing revealed an improvement in cycle life for both nanophase composites compared to similar composites with micron-scale particles. Reducing the micro-structural features (i.e. particle/grain/phase size) features from the micron-scale to the nanophase in composite anodes leads to an increase in the cycle lifetime.

In recent years there has been a renewed interest in the use of metals such as; Al, Bi, Sn, Si and Ge that alloy with Li as replacement anodes for graphite in Li-ion batteries¹⁻³. Alloys offer significant advantages such as; higher specific capacity and improved safety compared to graphite. However, there is one major problem that must be solved before they can be used in both commercial and military applications. The major problem with alloys is the very large change in volume on charge/discharge which leads to mechanical stresses that causes the alloy to fracture and hence, disintegration of the anode⁴. One potential solution to solve the fracture problem is to use a composite anode¹⁻³. The composite anode in most cases consists of a lithium active metal dispersed within an inactive matrix. The purpose of the inactive matrix is to reduce the mechanical stresses associated Li insertion/removal during charging/discharging. However, active/inactive composites containing micron-sized particles still suffer from a restricted cycle life that limits their use in commercial and military applications. Hence, there is a need to develop ways to improve the cycle life of active/inactive composites so they can be used in practical applications.

One potential approach to increase the cycle life of active/inactive composites is to reduce the microstructural features (i.e. particle/grain/phase size) of the active/inactive composites to the nano-scale (< 100 nm). It is the purpose of this paper to examine this suggestion using two different active/inactive composites; one containing an inactive metal (Cu) matrix and the other an

inactive ceramic (Li_2O) matrix. In both cases the Li active metal is Sn. These composites were chosen because they both have higher theoretical capacities than the currently used graphite and cycle data is available for these materials having micron-sized particle/grains/phases and thus, a direct comparison can be made if reducing these features to the nano-scale from the micron-scale does improve cycle life.

Results and discussion

The X-ray diffraction pattern for the Cu_6Sn_5 powders after precipitation, shown in Fig. 1, revealed that the precipitate was single-phase Cu_6Sn_5 . No other Cu-Sn phases or pure component (Cu or Sn) peaks were exhi-

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction pattern of the as-precipitated Cu_6Sn_5 material.

^ψDedicated to Professor H. C. Gaur on his 80th birthday.

bited in the X-ray diffraction pattern. The average crystallite size calculated using the Scherer formula was 10 nm. Scanning electron microscopy analysis revealed the particles exhibited an equiaxed morphology with all particles less than 100 nm. The average particle size on more than 200 particles was estimated to be about 40 nm. Transmission electron microscopy confirmed that all particles were nanophase (<100 nm).

The X-ray diffraction pattern of the jar milled Li_3N and SnO powders is shown in Fig. 2. Also shown in Fig. 2 is the X-ray pattern for Sn. Examination of Fig. 2 revealed diffraction peaks matching the pattern for Sn. No Li_3N and SnO peaks were exhibited, confirming the reaction of eq. (1). In addition, a broad region of enhanced X-ray intensity near the beginning of the milled powder pattern was observed, which is indicative of an amorphous phase and is believed to be amorphous Li_2O consistent with the reaction of eq. (1). Amorphous Li_2O has also been identified in electrochemically reduced tin oxides⁶. Scanning electron and transmission electron microscopy analysis revealed that the Sn and Li_2O phases were nanophase with particles on the order of 50 nm. In summary, both Sn composites; one containing the inactive metal (Cu) matrix and the other an inactive ceramic (Li_2O) matrix were nanophase.

Fig. 2. X-Ray powder diffraction patterns of SnO reduced by Li_3N (milled powder) and Sn.

The volumetric capacity of the nanophase Cu_6Sn_5 alloy (≈ 40 nm) versus cycle number is plotted in Fig. 3. Also shown in Fig. 3 is data for micron-sized Cu_6Sn_5 . From Fig. 3 it can be observed that the micron-sized Cu_6Sn_5 alloys exhibit considerable capacity fade. For example, the extrapolated capacity approaches zero at about 45–50 cycles for an alloy produced by melting ($< 38 \mu\text{m}$) and 80–85 cycles for an alloy prepared by mechanical alloying ($\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$)⁵. In contrast, at 100 cycles the nanophase Cu_6Sn_5 powders still have a significant amount of reversible capacity which is nearly constant with the number of cycles. This result shows that a large improvement in capacity retention of the Cu_6Sn_5 alloy is obtained when the particle size is reduced to the nano-scale range from the micron sized range. This is expected since, it is known that the driving force for fracture is the release of the strain energy which results from the volume change as Li is inserted/deinserted, which scales as the cube of the particle/grain size, thus if the particle/grain size is reduced the strain energy is reduced leading to less of a chance for fracture and hence, a longer life material. In addition, in Fig. 3 the theoretical capacity of graphite is shown. From Fig. 3 it can be seen that the volumetric capacity of the nanophase Cu_6Sn_5 alloy at 100 cycles (≈ 1450 mAh/mL) is almost twice the theoretical capacity of graphite (≈ 850 mAh/mL) thus, nanophase Cu_6Sn_5 is a potential replacement anode for graphite in Li-ion batteries. Preliminary cycle life testing of the *in situ* formed nano-scale Sn- Li_2O composite has also shown an improvement over a similar composite prepared by simply mixing micron sized Sn and Li_2O powders.

Fig. 3. Volumetric capacity versus cycle number for nanophase and micron-sized Cu_6Sn_5 . Also included is the theoretical capacity for graphite.

Experimental

The active (Sn)/inactive metal (Cu) matrix composite is formed as Li is added to a Sn-Cu alloy. Nanophase Cu_6Sn_5 powders were synthesized by a chemical method, which involved reducing a methanol solution of CuCl_2 and SnCl_2 (1.2 : 1 volume ratio) with NaBH_4 in a 14 M NaOH solution under constant stirring at room temperature⁵. The nanophase active (Sn)/inactive ceramic (Li_2O) matrix composite is formed by the *in situ* electrochemical reduction of SnO by Li_3N according the reaction given below⁶ :

Li_3N and SnO powders were jar milled under an argon atmosphere at ambient temperature for five days. The nanophase composite powders produced by both methods were characterized by X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy and transmission electron microscopy. The cycle life of the nanophase composite powders was evaluated in half-cells at room temperature. Positive electrodes were prepared by mixing 85-wt. % composite powders, 5-wt. % carbon and 10-wt. % polyvinylidene fluoride dissolved in *N*-methylpyrrolidinone. This mixture was coated onto a Cu substrate. The cathodes were dried

under vacuum at 80°C for 24 h. Metallic lithium was used as the negative electrode. The electrolyte solution was 1 M LiPF_6 : ethylene carbonate/dimethyl carbonate/diethyl carbonate (5 : 4 : 1 by volume). The cells were cycled at a constant current density of 0.1 mA/cm² between 0.005 to 1.5 V.

Conclusions :

The results of this study reveal a significant improvement in the cycle life of Sn composites anodes, for use in Li-ion batteries, was achieved when the structural features (particle/grain/phase size) are reduced from the micron-scale to the nano-scale range (< 100 nm).

References

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